

Detailed Insight into the CZTS/CdS Interface Modification by Air-annealing in the Monograin Layer Solar Cells

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ABSTRACT Relatively fast progress in the development of kesterite solar cells has been made over the last decade, but the experimental efficiency is still $\sim 13\%$. One proposed reason is a poor band alignment with $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ (CZTS) and CdS that results in strong interface recombination losses. Results of this work show that the temperature and the duration of air-annealing of the CZTS/CdS heterojunction are essential for device performance. Soft annealing slightly improved

the device efficiency due to elemental inter-mixing at the interface. On the other hand, extended annealing increased absorber bandgap energy resulting in higher V_{OC} values, indicating to the reduction in the degree of Cu-Zn disordering in CZTS, which also could be expected to have beneficial influence on the device performance. However, interface analysis revealed the formation of a Cu-rich CZTS absorber surface, providing the reason for the degradation of the CZTS solar cell devices. Annealing effect on the interface defects was analyzed by capacitance-frequency-voltage ($C-V-f$) analysis combined with the SCAPS simulations. $C-V-f$ based loss maps showed that air-annealing modifies the asymmetrical distribution of the density of interface states at the CZTS/CdS interface, which becomes fully symmetrical for longer annealing times at 200°C.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cu_2ZnSnS_4 (CZTS) is highlighted as being one of the most promising semiconductor compounds for photovoltaics having high absorption coefficient, tunable band gap, low radiation damage, and long-term stability. The crystal structure of kesterite is very similar to $Cu(In,Ga)(S,Se)_2$ (CIGS). Therefore, combining the suitable absorber properties and the same device configuration as CIGS,¹ relatively fast progress in the development of kesterite solar cells has been made over the last decade and the highest efficiency 12.6% for p -CZTSSe/ n -CdS heterojunction-based thin-film solar cells has been achieved by IBM group in 2013² and recently renewed by Zhou *et al.* in 2021.³

The most used buffer layer material in CZTS thin film solar cells is still CdS deposited by chemical bath deposition (CBD) method, which has been proven as a simple, fast and inexpensive technique to produce uniform and reproducible thin films. There are several advantages for using a buffer layer - a protection of the absorber surface against damage from high energy sputtering

process to apply ZnO; chemical etching of the surface in the CBD process; the Cd diffusion into the absorber. The latter is correlated to a Cu depletion in the absorber surface layer that leads to a substitution of Cu^+ by Cd^{2+} due to their closely matched ionic radii: 0.97 Å and 0.96 Å, respectively.^{4,5} In CIGS material, this process has been related to a type inversion (p to n) of the absorber surface region, effectively moving the junction into the absorber; thus, the minority carriers from the bulk become majority carriers at the device interface, having there a lower recombination rate.^{6,7} For CZTS, there is no such inversion of conduction type at the surface region and therefore the p - n junction is located at the CZTS/CdS interface.⁸ With high bandgap kesterite like $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$, CdS exhibits a poor band alignment with absorber and results in strong interface recombination losses. It affects directly the device performance.⁹ CZTS solar cells have shown a negative offset, so-called “cliff-like”, where the conduction band minimum (CBM) of CZTS is higher than that of CdS.¹⁰ Theoretical calculations show that the negative band offset limits open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and fill factor (FF) due to recombination at the heterojunction interface. Both, the p - n junction position at the CZTS/CdS interface and negative conduction band offset lead to a much more pronounced dependence of the electrical characteristics of the device on the quality of the CZTS/CdS interface due to interface-related and tunnelling-assisted recombination.⁸

The post-annealing of CZTS/CdS interface shows the potential for the high-performance device. Several groups reported that annealing a CZTS/CdS sample in different atmosphere - in vacuum¹¹, in air^{12,13} or in inert gas^{9,14} is an effective method to enhance the quality of the interface. It was found that post-annealing improved the device performance through the passivation of interfacial defects and the reduction of non-radiative recombination. It is also reported that post-annealing at around 200- 300 °C could enable moderate inter-diffusion of Cd and Zn, which could form a thin layer of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cd}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ on the CZTS surface as well as an ultrathin $\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{S}$ layer

in between CZTS and CdS.^{14–16} These intermediate layers, were proposed to change the “cliff-like” band alignment to a “spike-like” band alignment between CZTS and CdS. Additionally, occupation of Cu vacancies at the CZTS surface by Cd atoms from CdS could form the donor defect Cd_{Cu} , which helps the type inversion in the CZTS surface, thus minimizing defect-induced recombination loss.^{13,16} In the recently published study¹⁷, Cd-doping was found to suppress the formation of Zn related secondary phase and Cu_{Zn} antisite defects, resulting in the increase in the V_{OC} and FF values. Since substitution of Zn by Cd increases lattice constant of CZTS¹⁸, it can decrease lattice mismatch between CZTS and CdS, decreasing hole–electron recombination at CZTS/CdS interface and being favourable to enhancement of device performance.¹⁷

This work reports detailed analysis of air-annealing effect of CZTS/CdS on the interface properties and on the performance of CZTS monograin layer solar cells. To gather more information about the electrical behaviour of the devices, the temperature-dependent $J-V$ and admittance spectroscopy measurements were performed. The elemental inter-diffusion after an air-annealing of CZTS/CdS heterojunction was studied by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Cu_2ZnSnS_4 monograin powder was synthesized from high purity (99.999%) binary compounds- CuS, ZnS and SnS in the liquid phase of potassium iodide (KI) flux material in sealed quartz ampoule at 740 °C. The temperature of the chamber furnace was increased from room temperature (RT) to 740 °C within 3 hours and kept at elevated temperature for 142 hours. The growth process was stopped by cooling the ampoule to room temperature in air. The flux material was removed by leaching and rinsing with deionized water. The released monograin powder was dried in a hot-air thermostat and sieved into several narrow granulometric fractions between 38 and 125 μm . More details about monograin powder growth process is reported in¹⁹.

Before using the powder grains as absorber material in monograin layer (MGL) solar cells, the powder was etched with 1 vol% Br in methanol followed by 10 wt% KCN aqueous solution for 5 min at RT with the aim to clean crystals surfaces from the residues precipitated from molten KI.²⁰ After the etching process, the CZTS powder was annealed in sealed ampoule in a two-temperature-zone furnace at 840 °C in sulphur vapour ($p_S=2000$ Torr) for 60 min to adjust the surface and bulk composition of crystals. The post-treated monograin powder was covered with CdS buffer layer by chemical bath deposition method by using vertical rotator in hot-air thermostat at 60 °C for 30 min. The 360° multi-functional vertical rotator provides compact and uniform CdS coverage on CZTS crystals. An alkali deposition solution contained 0.01 M CdI₂ as Cd source and 1 M SC(NH₂)₂ as S precursor, 2 M NH₄OH aqueous solution was added to adjust the bath solution pH to 11.6 at room temperature. These process conditions resulted in CdS buffer layer with thickness of approximately 45 nm. Directly after buffer layer deposition, CdS covered CZTS powder was divided into portions and annealed in an air at temperatures from 175 to 275 °C for 10 to 120 min.

Solar Cell Fabrication: Monograin layer solar cells with following structure: Au/CZTS/CdS/*i*-ZnO/ZnO:Al (schematic structure is presented in **Figure 1**) were prepared. At first, monograin membranes were formed by embedding the CdS covered CZTS crystals halfway into an epoxy layer. After polymerization of epoxy, the double layer of ZnO (*i*-ZnO and ZnO:Al) as window layer was deposited by radio-frequency magnetron sputtering on the top of the membranes. Finally, highly conductive Ag-nanowires (Ag-NWs) were applied on top of the ZnO layer, which improve the carrier collection of ZnO. Finally, the structure was glued onto a durable transparent substrate. For back contacting, the bottom side of the MGL was polished to remove polymer from powder crystals and to form a p^+ layer before applying back contact (BC). This type

of BC facilitate hole tunneling from absorber bulk into conductive metal (Au). Metal contacts were deposited through a metal mask using thermal evaporation method. Total area of single cell was 4.5 mm^2 .

Figure 1. Schematic structure of monograin layer solar cell.

Device Characterization: The solar cells were characterized by measuring the current *versus* voltage (J - V) characteristics with a Keithley 2400 source meter under standard test conditions (AM 1.5, 100 mW cm^{-2}) using a Newport solar simulator. Spectral response measurements were performed using a computer-controlled SPM-2 prism monochromator. The generated photocurrent was detected at 0 V bias voltage at RT by using a 250 W halogen lamp and DSP lock-in amplifier. For temperature dependent measurements, solar cells were mounted in the closed-cycle He cryostat and the admittance spectra were recorded using a Wayne Kerr 6500B impedance analyzer while temperature-dependent J - V curve measurements were made using a Keithley 2401 source meter. Impedance Z and phase angle y were both measured as functions of frequency and temperature. The used frequency range was from 20 Hz to 10 MHz and the temperature was varied from 20 K to 320 K with a step $\Delta T=10 \text{ K}$. In order to maintain the linearity of the response signal, the AC voltage amplitude was 30 mV. The temperature dependent admittance measurements (AS) were carried out in the dark and with DC bias of 0 V and -0.5 V. The same setup was used also for room temperature bias dependent admittance spectroscopy measurements. CZTS/CdS interface

compositional changes were analyzed by Kratos Analytical AXIS Ultra DLD XPS spectrometer. In order to collect the signal of photoexcited electrons, the CZTS powder covered with CdS mounted on rotational sample holder by ultra-high vacuum proof carbon tape was excited by monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1486.6 eV) at 15 kV and 150 W. Hybrid lens mode in conjunction with aperture slot view (400 x 800 μ m) and pass energy 40 eV were set to collect the high-resolution photoelectron spectra. Charge neutralizer was kept on during all XPS measurements. In order to study the chemical composition in depth of CdS and down to the interface between buffer and absorber material MiniBeam I Ar⁺ ion sputtering source was applied at 2 keV and 10 mA. During the removal of surface layer, the sample holder rotation was turned on at moderate speed in order to have more even surface removal of powder samples.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At first, the air-annealing at different temperatures directly after CdS deposition was performed and its influence on device parameters was studied. In **Figure 2**, the influence of 10, 30 and 60 minutes of CZTS/CdS air-annealing at different temperatures on the device performance are shown as box plots. As the working area of the MGL solar cells is around 75% of the total area,²¹ the MGL solar cell efficiency values were re-calculated for the active area (η_{active}).

Figure 2. Comparison of solar cell efficiencies after air-annealing of CZTS/CdS at different temperatures for a) 10, b) 30 and c) 60 minutes.

Short time annealing ($t_{ann}=10$ min) at temperature range 175-275 °C improved the efficiency from 6.7% to 7.3%. Increasing the annealing time up to 30 minutes, the device performance was improved up to 7.5% at temperatures 175-200 °C. Annealing at 225 °C and higher for 30 minutes was detrimental for solar cell efficiencies. Annealing for longer time ($t_{ann}=60$ min) showed slightly higher efficiencies for solar cells based on CZTS/CdS heterojunction that were annealed at 175 °C. Annealing at 200 °C and higher was already detrimental for solar cell performances. From these results it was concluded that CZTS/CdS air-annealing at 200 °C is beneficial for improving the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of MGL devices.

As a next step, more precise investigations by using different annealing times at 200 °C were performed to understand the annealing effects on the device performances. The photovoltaic parameters of CZTS devices based on heterojunction annealed in an air at 200 °C for different times are presented as box plots in **Figure 3**. The average value is calculated from 15 solar cells. The average values of V_{OC} increased from 717 mV to 743 mV by increasing the annealing time to 120 minutes (Figure 3a). The average j_{SC} value 18.1 mA cm⁻² was constant until the annealing time was increased to 60 minutes (Figure 3b). The average FF value decreased from 57 % to 48 % if annealing time was longer than 30 minutes (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. Box plot of a) open circuit voltage, b) current density, c) fill factor and d) efficiency of CZTS devices with CdS annealing in an air at 200 °C for different times.

The basic solar cell parameters, however, are not the only information we can obtain from $J-V$ data. For example, from the light $J-V$ curve analysis, the quality of the $p-n$ junction and losses related to resistive components of the device can be concluded. In this study, the single exponential diode equation was employed to analyze the light $J-V$ data. The diode parameters including the series resistance (R_s) and the diode ideality factor (n) found from these analyses are plotted in the

Figure 4. Series resistance decreases from 2.8 to 1.8 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ by annealing at 200 °C up to 20 minutes

and then starts to increase again. Ideality factor is around $n= 2.6-2.8$ for devices without annealing and annealing at 200 °C for 10 and 20 minutes. Longer time annealing at 200 °C degrades the quality of solar cells, the n value increases over 4.4-4.5, which is seen also in degraded FF values indicating to high recombination losses.

Figure 4. Photovoltaic parameters - R_s and n for CZTS MGL solar cells based on air-annealed CdS at 200 °C different times. (one-diode model fitting results).

To gather more information about the electrical behaviour of the cells, the temperature-dependent J - V measurements were performed under illumination. The behaviour of the V_{OC} of the cells as a function of the temperature $V_{OC}(T)$ is shown in **Figure 5a** and can be described by equation²²:

$$V_{OC} = \frac{E_a}{q} - \frac{Ak_B T}{q} \ln \left(\frac{J_{00}}{J_L} \right) \quad (1)$$

where E_a is the activation energy, q is the elementary charge, A is the ideality factor, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, J_{00} is the reverse saturation current prefactor and J_L is

the light generated photocurrent density. At relatively high temperatures (above 200 K), the V_{OC} versus T shows linear behaviour. The extrapolation of this linear part to $T = 0$ K indicates the activation energy E_a . The calculated E_a of these devices according to Equation (1) are all smaller than the bandgaps of their absorbers extracted from the EQE spectra (**Figure 5b**), which indicates that there is recombination at the heterojunction interface of these solar cells.

Figure 5. a) The temperature dependent V_{OC} of the CZTS monograin layer solar cells and its linear extrapolation to $T=0$ K and b) EQE spectra of corresponding cells.

As mentioned, external quantum efficiency (EQE) was used to determine the band gap (E_g) values of CZTS absorber materials. The EQE of the CZTS MGL solar cells was measured as a function of the incident light wavelength at room temperature. From the linear segment of the low-energy side of the construction $(EQE)^2$ vs. E curves, the effective bandgap energy (E_g^*) can be evaluated. An increase of the E_g^* from 1.568 eV to 1.619 eV ($\Delta E_g = 51$ meV) by CZTS/CdS heterojunction annealing at 200 °C longer than 60 minutes was observed. Estimated bandgap energy values from EQE for absorbers and corresponding CZTS device parameters (E_a , V_{OC} and

$V_{OC\ def}$) based on annealed heterojunctions at 200 °C for different time are summarized in **Table 1**. The V_{OC} deficits are calculated in this paper with respect to the effective bandgap energy values from EQE. Then, $V_{OC\ def} = E_g^* - V_{OC}$. It is seen that although the V_{OC} values increase with longer annealing process, the V_{OC} deficit remains large or even becomes larger by considering the bandgap increase.

Table 1. Effective bandgap energy, activation energy, open circuit voltage and V_{OC} deficit for CZTS monograin layer solar cells with different CdS annealing times at 200 °C.

t_{ann} at 200 °C [min]	E_g^* [eV]	E_a [meV]	V_{OC} [mV]	$V_{OC\ def}(E_g^* - V_{OC})$ [mV]
w.o.	1.568	1320	731	837
10	1.567	1295	732	835
20	1.564	1263	731	833
30	1.571	1246	736	835
60	1.609	1175	748	861
120	1.619	1185	757	862

One reason for the bandgap increase could be the existence of ordering-disordering phenomenon in kesterites. By first-principle calculations the band gap energy difference between ordered and disordered kesterite phases was predicted to be around 100 meV in CZTS.²³ From photoluminescence (PL) studies,²⁴ it was proposed that the difference between PL band energies resulting from the same radiative recombination of ordered and disordered structures is about 80 meV, the latter being smaller. Transition between ordered and disordered CZTS could be done by using low-temperature post-annealing at temperatures below the critical temperature ($T_c \sim 260$ °C) and degree of disordering depends on annealing time.²⁵ Our results show that CZTS/CdS annealing at 200 °C up to half an hour is beneficial to improve the FF values, which can be attributed to reduced series resistance (R_s). Longer time of CZTS/CdS annealing probably reduces the degree of disordering in CZTS, resulting in CZTS absorber material with higher bandgap,²⁶ but at the

same time we see an increase of recombination losses at the interface. It was found that change in Cu-Zn ordering is accompanied with a change in the radiative recombination mechanism from band to tail to deep defect related recombination in most ordered material reducing its positive effect to the CZTS solar cell performance.²⁶

We also studied the elemental inter-diffusion induced by annealing of CdS/Cu₂ZnSnS₄ heterostructure in air at 200 °C for different times. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy elemental depth profiles of samples before and after the air annealing at 200 °C for 30 and 120 minutes were conducted. In order to reveal the changes in CZTS absorber material surface composition, the ratio of [Cu]/([Zn]+[Sn]) were calculated and presented in **Figure 6** (yellow area is CdS (~ 35 nm) and grey area is the surface of CZTS monograins (~550 nm)).

Figure 6. XPS elemental depth profiles of heterojunction without and with 30, 120 minutes air-annealing at 200 °C.

XPS depth profiles of [Cu]/([Zn]+[Sn]) revealed that the air-annealing at 200 °C for 30 and 120 min resulted in the formation of a Cu-rich ($[Cu]/([Zn]+[Sn]) > 1$) CZTS absorber surface close to

the interface. The Cu-rich absorber surface layer thickness was found to increase with annealing time. Out-diffusion of Cu from the absorber is a well-known phenomenon in the Cu-chalcogenide/CdS heterojunction.²⁷ Cu has highest mobility and its out-diffusion into the CZTS surface could be the cause of the formation of Cu-rich surface. If to consider the phase diagram Cu₂S-ZnS-SnS₂,²⁸ there exists a Cu-rich CZTS phase in some extent (few mol %). So, we propose that air annealing results in Cu-rich CZTS in the surface, but not the formation of secondary phases. It is known that Cu-poor and Zn-rich CZTS absorber composition is needed for high efficiency devices.^{29,30} Therefore, we propose that despite the reduction in the degree of Cu-Zn disordering leading to improved V_{OC} and increased E_g with longer time annealing (Table 1), it is not beneficial to the device performance due to formation of Cu-rich absorber surface.

Slight improvement in the performance of the CZTS MGL solar cells after short time annealing at 200 °C could also be due to possible formation of ultra-thin Cu₂Cd_xZn_{1-x}SnS₄ layer at the CZTS/CdS interface or due to improved CdS crystallinity, but it was not possible to provide solid evidence of the Cd diffusion into CZTS by XPS.

To further look into the recombination mechanisms in the studied solar cells, admittance spectroscopy (AS) was implemented. AS involves measuring the junction capacitance as a function of frequency f and temperature T . The admittance of the heterostructure is a superposition of the free carrier capacitance across the width of the space charge region (SCR) C_d and the contribution from the charging and discharging of deeper defect levels within the SCR of the junction. If deeper carrier traps are present, the band bending in the SCR causes the Fermi level E_F to cross the trap level E_t at some distance from the interface, at the crossing point x_t . The oscillating voltage with the frequency f causes the electric charge accumulated by traps to oscillate in the vicinity of x_t . The trapped electric charge follows the applied voltage oscillations and

contributes to the total capacitance only if their frequency does not exceed the characteristic trap frequency f_t . Therefore, in the case of low frequencies $f_{lf} \ll f_t$, the trap related capacitance C_t is equal to C_{lf} , where C_{lf} is the low frequency capacitance which depends on the trap density N_t and the acceptor concentration N_a if depletion layer is in the p -type material. In high frequency ($f_{hf} \gg f_t$) region the junction capacitance C is determined by C_{hf} , where C_{hf} is the high frequency capacitance. Accordingly, in the case of a single majority carrier trap level the total junction capacitance can be described by the equation:^{31,32}

$$C(f) = C_d + \frac{C_{lf} - C_d}{1 + (2\pi f)^2 \tau^2} \quad (2)$$

where τ is the characteristic trapping time that depends on the trap density N_t , the acceptor concentration N_a and on the SCR-width w . In the case of a small trap concentration N_t , the characteristic frequency f_t for the hole trapping defects is $f_t = (2\pi\tau)^{-1}$.^{31,32} The inflection frequencies f_i can be determined from maxima in the derivative $-fdC/df$ spectra that should demonstrate a peak at the frequency f_i . In general, these peaks in the $-fdC/df$ graphs could be related to defect responses, series resistances in the device, or carrier freeze-out.

In the present paper, at first, we followed the method developed in³³ and measured room temperature bias- and frequency-dependent capacitances of our CZTS solar cells annealed at 200 °C for different times. The results of experimental measurements are represented as 2-D contour plots showing the derivative of the capacitance with respect to the frequency multiplied by the frequency. These plots are called “loss maps,” because responses in these contour plots correspond to responses of different non-idealities in the devices, see **Figure 7**. We see, that with increasing of annealing time at 200 °C the rather busy loss maps show a certain modification. The most prominent peak can be found at about 70 kHz and 0.6-0.7 V. We made a temperature dependent

admittance spectroscopy measurement for the 60 min annealed sample to find a depth of this defect state. It is known that the temperature dependence of the inflection frequency f_i is described by the equation³¹:

$$2\pi f_t(T) = e_t(T)/\pi = \pi^{-1} N_{c,v} v_{Th} \sigma_{n,p} \exp(-E_A/kT) = \xi_0 T^2 \exp(-E_A/kT), \quad (3)$$

where e_t is the emission rate, $N_{c,v}$ is the effective density of states in the conduction or valence band, v_{Th} is the thermal velocity of the minority carriers at the interface, $\sigma_{n,p}$ is the capture cross-section for electrons or holes, $E_A = E_t - E_v$ is the activation energy of the defect level E_t with respect to the valence band edge E_v in p -type absorber and ξ_0 covers all the temperature independent parameters. The activation energy of a defect level E_A can be obtained from the temperature dependence of the capacitance spectra i.e. from the Arrhenius plot of the quantity $\ln(2\pi f_i T^2)$ versus $1000/T$. It turned out, that the activation energy of this defect is about 155 meV, see **Figure 8**. Thus, this defect is present in all measured solar cells.

Figure 7. $-fdC/df$ contour plot of the CZTS devices as a function of bias voltage and the frequency. Experimental data (a)-(e), SCAPS simulation results (f)-(j).

Figure 8. The Arrhenius plot for the sample annealed 60 min showing the calculated activation energies of the defect levels corresponding to capacitance step. Measured at 0 V and -0.5 V bias.

As a next step, the loss map simulations were performed using the SCAPS software.³⁴ The simulations in SCAPS were performed without external illumination. The capacitance and conductance of the heterojunction structure were calculated at the same operation points as for our experimental data, with 50 different frequencies varying logarithmically from 100 Hz to 1 MHz and with a bias voltage ranging from -1.5 V to +1 V with a voltage step of 50 mV. The simulated structure consists of a Au/CZTS/CdS/*i*-ZnO/ZnO:Al stack. The parameters used in SCAPS simulation for the different layers are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Properties of the different layers in the simulated structure.

Layer	Thickness [nm]	Carrier density [cm ⁻³]	Electron affinity [eV]	Band gap [eV]
CZTS	1000	2×10 ¹⁶	4.1	1.5
CdS	40	5×10 ¹⁷	4.2	2.4
<i>i</i> -ZnO	60	5×10 ¹⁷	4.4	3.3
ZnO:Al	750	1×10 ²⁰	4.4	3.3

The respective layer thicknesses are 1 μm , 40 nm, 60 nm and 750 nm, corresponding to the actual physical thickness values of the different layers, with the exception of the CZTS which is in reality thicker. But 1 μm thickness is sufficient thickness for the simulation to account for most of the band bending in the device. Different non-idealities were added to the device structure, which are a series resistance of $0.5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, a backside contact barrier with an activation energy that increases gradually with annealing time and three different interface state defects at the CZTS/CdS interface. The properties of the three interface state peaks also vary as a function of annealing time. The properties of the different non-idealities and their variation with annealing time are summarized in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Variation of the different non-idealities as a function of annealing time.

Non-idealities		Annealing time [min]				
		0	10	20	60	120
Back contact barrier	Activation energy [eV]	0.33	0.32	0.31	0.36	0.37
	Activation energy [eV]	0.155	0.155	0.155	0.155	0.155
Interface defect 1	Defect density [$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{ eV}^{-1}$]	2×10^{12}	2×10^{12}	2×10^{12}	2×10^{12}	2×10^{12}
	Activation energy [eV]	0.195	0.185	0.175	0.155	0.155
Interface defect 2	Defect density [$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{ eV}^{-1}$]	8×10^{11}	6×10^{11}	6×10^{11}	6×10^{11}	6×10^{11}
	Activation energy [eV]	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
Interface defect 3	Defect density [$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{ eV}^{-1}$]	4×10^8	8×10^8	8×10^8	8×10^8	8×10^8

The different non-idealities in the devices all contribute to a different part of the signal in the loss maps of Figure 6. The series resistance is adding the signal at a frequency of about 10 MHz. The backside barrier is adding the horizontal signal at a frequency of about 1 MHz. The third interface defect with an activation energy of 0.4 eV is adding the signal at 10 Hz and a voltage of about 0.7 V, whereas the other two interface peaks are contributing the largest signal that is

extending over most of the frequency range in forward bias. In fact, in the experimental measurement, this signal seems to be coming from a somewhat asymmetrical interface defect peak, with a maximum at an activation energy of about 0.155 eV and a tail towards deeper activation energies. Unfortunately, in SCAPS only Gaussian interface defect peaks can be simulated. Therefore, the exact simulation of this response is not possible. We have tried to approximate the experimental data by using two Gaussian peaks, a large one at an activation energy of about 0.155 eV and a smaller one at a slightly larger activation energy, simulating the asymmetry of the experimental data towards higher activation energies. The resulting simulated signal in the loss map is not really agreeing completely with the experimental data but is reproducing the correct trend. As the annealing time increases, the asymmetry of the defect peak is reducing and after 60 minutes of annealing the asymmetry has disappeared and the defect peak is fully Gaussian. Therefore, we may conclude from the admittance data analysis that there are several recombination routes in our CZTS MGL solar cells, among them interface recombination. Unfortunately, none of these routes is disappearing with air annealing of the CZTS/CdS interface at 200 °C for different times ranging from 10 to 120 minutes. However, the CZTS/CdS heterojunction is modified as the distribution of the density of interface states at the CZTS/CdS interface becomes symmetrical after 60 minutes of annealing at 200 °C.

4 CONCLUSION

Effect of CZTS/CdS air-annealing on the interface properties and on the performance of CZTS monograin layer solar cells was studied. Current–voltage characteristics showed that short time CZTS/CdS air-annealing ($t_{ann}=10$ min) at temperature between 175-275 °C slightly improved the efficiency from 6.7% to 7.3% due to possible formation of ultra-thin $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cd}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ layer at the CZTS/CdS interface, or due to improved CdS crystallinity. Optimal condition for improving the

performance of CZTS monograin layer solar cells was annealing at 175-200 °C for 20 min. Applying longer annealing times, V_{OC} values increased from 717 mV to 743 mV and bandgap value from 1.57 eV to 1.62 eV, but all other output parameters degraded. According to XPS study, air-annealing at 200 °C for 120 min resulted in most Cu-rich ($[Cu]/([Zn]+[Sn]) > 1$) CZTS absorber surface close to the interface, which is proposed as the reason for the degradation of devices. Improved V_{OC} values and increased E_g^* are due to the reduction in the degree of Cu-Zn disordering in CZTS.

Admittance spectroscopy studies showed that properties of a CZTS monograin layer solar cells change during the air-annealing process. $C-V-f$ measurements and SCAPS simulations indicated to the change in the distribution of interface defects at the CZTS/CdS interface. The most prominent interface defect has an activation energy about 155 meV and it was present in all samples.

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Author Contributions

M. K.-K. designed the overall experiments, mainly write the manuscript. K.T., M.P. and K.M. contributed to the fabrication of absorber materials and CZTS monograin layer solar cells. R.J., J.K. and M.G. contributed to the IV-temp, AS measurements and analysis. M. D. contributed to XPS and EQE measurements and analysis. G.B. and B.V. performed SCAPS simulations. All of the authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

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